

MARINE CONSERVATION MAPPING IN MACARONESIA.

UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA

CRETUS

Cross-disciplinary Research in Environmental Technologies

equalsea

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Key messages

Macaronesia already has a strong foundation of cooperation, policy innovation and scientific collaboration, but achieving durable 30x30 outcomes will depend on turning that momentum into practical action, especially in Cape Verde, adjacent high seas / oceanic areas, and transnational MPA networks.

Macaronesia: spanning the Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands and Cape Verde, Macaronesia is an ecologically connected Atlantic region with growing relevance for marine conservation.

▮ The region is not starting from zero. The report maps 65 projects overall and 36 active or upcoming initiatives, with Marine Protected Areas present in 61% of projects and Marine Spatial Planning in 34%, showing both a strong conservation base and room to deepen MSP-MPA integration.

▮ The active portfolio already combines three complementary functions: Policy-enabling initiatives that strengthen MSP-MPA articulation and cross-border governance, Knowledge-generating initiatives that build the evidence base, and Implementation-oriented initiatives that are closer to site-based management, restoration and community outcomes.

▮ The priorities set out for the next phase are well defined: strengthen Cape Verde's participation, address the High Seas and adjacent oceanic governance gap, improve data interoperability, back transnational MPA networks, and support projects that convert science into implementation.

Overview

65

projects mapped across the region

36

active or upcoming projects through 2030

67%

of mapped investment comes from EU programmes

69%

of the projects concentrate on the northern archipelagos (Canary Islands, Madeira Islands, Azores)

Gaps and opportunities

Oceanic, offshore and adjacent high seas

Only 14% of mapped initiatives focus exclusively on oceanic or pelagic environments. Targeted support for adjacent high seas, seamounts, canyons and ecological corridors would address a major regional gap.

Transnational MPA networks

The strongest active initiatives already connect MSP, MPAs and regional cooperation. The next step is to turn ecological connectivity into corridor-based protection, shared governance and coordinated monitoring across archipelagos and adjoining Atlantic waters.

Cape Verde and EU-Africa equity

Cape Verde remains underrepresented in the current landscape and has lower access to planning expertise, data systems and long-term institutional support. Locally anchored partnerships can improve regional balance, ownership and continuity.

From science to implementation

Macaronesia has a strong evidence base, but research does not always translate into operational conservation. The highest added value lies in projects with clear pathways to management measures, restoration, fisheries action, enforcement or community co-management.

Policy coherence and governance continuity

Current cooperation is often fragmented and constrained by short funding cycles, limiting long-term policy alignment between EU and African partners. Strengthening permanent regional cooperation mechanisms would improve governance coherence and strategic continuity.

Across all five areas, interoperable data and monitoring systems, together with stronger socioeconomic and governance integration, are cross-cutting needs.

Flexible financing for greater value

Because EU programmes account for around 67% of mapped investment, philanthropy can add most value where it is fast, targeted and catalytic: linking science to implementation, strengthening locally anchored partnerships in Cape Verde, supporting transnational MPA design and governance, improving data interoperability, and sustaining conservation outcomes beyond short project cycles.

With these gaps addressed, Macaronesia can emerge as a model Atlantic region for integrated marine conservation and sustainable ocean governance.

